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Institutions Of Higher Learning And The World Of Work: A Missing Link, Problems And Way Forward

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ABSTRACT

This paper seeks to establish that institutions of higher learning are not supposed to be in a close relationship with the world of work because of the simple reason that man has a great inclination to work for the survival of his/ her life in an environment. It further adds that career education is a great exponent of the different educational levels which youths and adults could avail themselves of the opportunity to train and be able to gain employment. This is not so in Nigeria as the increase in the number of higher institutions is outweighing the vocational and technical education and training that are supposed to take care of the youths through employment generation. Therefore, this paper suggests that there should be a close relation between students of higher institutions and employers of labor so that the much talk about unemployment in Nigeria will be greatly reduced in Nigeria.

Keywords: higher institutions, learning, youths, unemployment

INTRODUCTION

Work is the central and most essential part to man's existence on planet earth. It motivates him, sustains him and makes living meaningful and purposeful. Without work, all life goes rotten like " kidnapping, armed robbery, prostitution, greed, jealousy, hatred, misuse of sexual activities, misuse of money, misuse of power and the careless use of bombs against neighbors and the environment.

This is the reason why Kochhar (2010) opined that when work is soulless, life stifles and dies. Hence, if any man will not work, never should he eat according to Saint Paul in the New Testament of the holy bible

In this regard, a variety of studies have revealed that people do not want to live useless lives. To work is the basic desire of human beings. It is therefore, desirable that total education system must in addition to many other tasks, help young people to grow to up to utilize the culture of work and doing it correctly to acceptable standards as demanded by the society. The colleges, polytechnics, mono-techniques and universities have to train the various categories of youths to fit themselves properly into work places. This is the reason why the students are supposed to be trained so as to behave as workers and set the place as potential labor force for an economy to develop

Okonkwo (2013) opined that Nigeria does not need to have many Colleges of Education, Polytechnics and Universities but many vocational schools and training centers like what happens in Japan. Omotosho (2013) added that 70% of the country's workforces are graduates of technical colleges and vocational training centers, while only 20% possesses higher education certificates. The author added that in an engineering unit, only one engineer is needed to coordinate the work of more twenty middle-level workers.

In Nigeria, the missing link is that so much attention is paid to institutions of higher learning than primary, junior secondary, senior secondary, technical, vocational education and training. This is reason why there are more than ten million children in the Northern part of Nigeria that did not have a taste of primary school education, why in many other southern states, there are many children that have dropped out of school and could not complete senior secondary education. Hence there are lots of street hawkers, pocket pickers, child trafficking, militancy, terrorism, and insurgency and so on.

In this regard a major problem of institutions of higher learning in Nigeria is that it more of centers on issuance of certificate than training centers of youths on how to use the brain, hand, leg, body means bearing to produce goods and services that are needed in the society.

This paper is of the view that Nigeria politicians and leaders should go back to the drawing board and find ways and means of building technical, vocational education and training centers in every 774 local government headquarters in the country so as to "catch them young" into the culture of what they can do for the society. This is what brings a change in the mind and attitude towards advanced living in the economy.

Objectives of Education in the World of Work

Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014 edition) view education in the world of work through purposeful implementation of vocational and technical education programmes as:

- A. An integral part of general education.
- B. A means of preparing for occupational fields and for effective participation in the world of work.
- c. An aspect of lifelong learning and a preparation for responsible citizens.
- D. An instrument for promoting environmental sound sustainable development
- E. A method of alleviating poverty.

And the purpose of the programme is as follows:

- A. To provide trained manpower in the applied sciences, technology and business particularly at craft, advanced craft and technical levels.
- B. To provide the technical knowledge and vocational skills that is necessary for agriculture, commercial and economic development.
- C. To give training and impart the necessary skills to individuals who shall be self-reliant economically.

This is the reason why trainees, after completing technical college programme, shall have three options:

- A. Secure employment either at the end of the whole course or after completing one or more modules of employable skills.
- B. Set up their own businesses and become self employed and be able to pursue further education in advanced craft or technical programme and in post-secondary (tertiary) technical institutions such as Science and Technical Colleges, Polytechnics/Monotechnics or College of Education (Technical) and Universities.

Career Development in the World of Work in Nigeria

Okparaeke (2018) opined that career development is a great responsibility of the total school and cannot be to a single discipline, department of school level because it is taken as a continuous process from early childhood throughout life. Therefore, all teachers, the primary school teachers, the secondary school teachers, the secondary school counselor, the college/ polytechnic/University teachers, instructors, professors etc are accountable for career development in the world of work of youths and adults in any nation.

Definition of career: Seligman (2010) defines career as a sequence of roles or positions including work, leisure, volunteer and education pursuit, and encompasses several occupations or vocations in many jobs or positions. According to the Oxford Advanced Learner's dictionary (2012) career is defined as the

series of jobs that a person has in a particular area of work usually involving more responsibility as time passes

Therefore, career is the evolving sequences of a person's work experiences over time which extends from childhood to retirement, and it is also the total constellation of psychological, sociological and educational, physical, economic and chance factors that combines to shape the career of any given individual over the life span.

This is the reason Super (1957) asserted that careers satisfy three major personal needs as follows.

- 1, Human relation needs e.g. Socialization, recognition, independence and status
2. Activity needs e.g. structure, stimulation, creativity, and use of skills
3. Livelihood needs, such as self awareness, self confidence, and self actualization. But for a society or nation, careers that can sustain the economy and provide needed products and services are required. Careers gives form and substance to people's lives.

Career Education

Career education is a conceptual model which is comprised of four separate but integrated phases as follows

- I. Career Awareness: This is the elementary school
- ii. Career Exploration: This is the junior secondary school
- iii. Career Orientation: It concerns the senior secondary school stage
- iv. Career preparation: This is the entry into professional career that is obtainable in the colleges, Polytechnics, Monotechnics and Universities.
- v. Careers preparation and professional cadres: This is postgraduate stage.
- vi. Career Training and Re-training: This is the adult stage where the adult engages in retraining so as to cope with modern technological changes e.g. computer compliance or literacy training programme.

Challenges and Upsurge of Institutions of Higher Learning in Nigeria

Records available during the time of this research work revealed that there are five hundred and ninety three (593) institutions of higher learning in Nigeria (Idiode, 2025). Below is the breakdown of the figure.

- A. 63 federal universities/ universities of technology
- B. 67 State Universities
- C. 159 Private Universities
- D. 38 Federal Polytechnics
- E. 48 State Polytechnics
- F. 55 Private Polytechnics
- G. 27 Federal Colleges of Education
- H. 54 State colleges of Education
- I. 82 Private colleges of Education

The above breakdown is an indication that Nigeria's population is increasing, and the following pertinent questions must be borne in mind by all Nigerians especially the policy makers.

1, Where are the offices, small –scale, medium-scale and large-scale businesses that will absorb the ever increasing graduate unemployment in Nigeria.

li, what quantities of food products that will be generated or planted that will take care of the growing population?

lii, what measures are put in place to check the ever increasing population to make sure that low income groups are discouraged from procreating too many children their income could maintain irrespective of religion and tradition encourage to have many children of choice?

Iv, What measures are the police putting in place in terms of gadgets and security outfits that would take care of deviant youths and adults in the economy.

It is when a well planned educational career and the political will that will distribute the wealth of the nation so as to actualize an advanced living of the people (Kehinde, 2024)

Consequently, population explosion in schools and institution of higher learning enrolment Hs resulted in lack of infrastructures, crowded classrooms with many students using few tables and desks, broken down roofs of most buildings, damaged cemented floors while some are not cemented at all , small sized

classrooms, ill equipped laboratories, libraries etc. Too many students are expected to use few available instruments, gadgets, tools, machines and other equipment, thereby forcing institutions to employ stand-by technicians for routine maintenance work. It as well encourages learning ‘‘ by rumor’’ in several ways. Bankole in Emeka (2016) opined that ‘‘Learning by rumor’’ refers to a situation of shortage of tables and desks/ chairs in the classroom that could not accommodate students to receive useful lectures or practical lessons. Many of the students have to stand by the windows and doors to listen to the teaching but have blurred understanding. At the end of such lectures, those who stood by the windows and doors would ask the ones who were inside to explain to them what the teacher has taught. Some of the students would respond that themselves did not understand what was taught by the lecturer. This kind of challenge encourages examination malpractice, while in some other cases, especially in laboratories, it ends up in damaging the various tools of training because of poor skill control/ handling and immediate replacement is not always guaranteed as a result of poor funding.

The Way Forward Between Institution of Higher Learning and the World of Work

The three levels of government (federal, state , and local government) should create the enabling environment by providing infrastructural facilities (including electricity) so as to close or bridge the gap that exist between institution of higher learning and the world of work. Employers of labour often complain that some of the graduates from institutions of higher learning are unemployable because they lack the requisite skills needed in the labour market. Lack of the these skills create a gap in their knowledge which must be filled to make them suitable to compete favorably for few vacancies that may be available from time to time (Sodipo, 2014).

Furthermore, there should be a strong synergy between the managers of the industries, factories and other employers of labour and institutions of higher learning on the aspects of skills needed, so that the learners will be trained based on the skills of need.

2. Technical and vocational education curriculum should be reviewed and implemented in line with generational paradigm shift in technology.

3. The national educational curriculum should be structured and integrated init entirety a functional entrepreneurship education which will provide students opportunity for creative thinking and practices rather than being imaginative and theoretical

4. Funds allotted for Technical Vocational Education Training (TVET) should be expended judiciously while its programme be meticulously implemented and objectively monitored in line with the current socio-economic demands.

5, Graduates of technical and vocational education should be trained to create gainful opportunities as well as hire employees, instead of graduating as job seekers.

6. The Vice- Chancellors of universities, Rectors of Polytechnics, Provosts of Colleges of Education should encourage the vocational and technical education teachers by providing them with some funds as well as training them on modern techniques and approaches compatible to their respective careers.

7. Policy makers, educational administrators and employers of labor should less emphasize on certificate qualification but emphasize more on practical performance.

8. Corporate bodies, wealthy individuals, communities and other NGOs should be urged to lend their support in empowering youths by providing funds for youth training.

9. Training and retraining of TVE teachers should be done on regular basis.

10. People in the industries should be involved in the running of TVE programmes

11. Technical and vocational education teachers with practical experience in different subject areas should be employed and professional, experienced administrators to run the technical and vocational institutions.

12. Government should provide welfare packages for TVE teachers to make the job attractive

13, Emphasis should be shifted from bookish, theoretic and white collar jobs oriented education to practical knowledge for skills acquisition.

Nigeria tertiary institutions should offer entrepreneurship education for life long trade in addition to courses that will enable students to meet their general academic requirements while learning the trade

(Obi,2013). Higher institution should work in hand gloves with willing industries to establish curriculum and programmes that will meet their demands.

CONCLUSION

This paper highlighted institutions of higher learning and the world of work that are supposed to utilize the youths and adult population for an efficient economic system, but experience has revealed that there is a gap the products of institutions of higher learning and the world of work. This is the reason why career education must be run in a way that will show that there is synergy or close relationship between institutions of higher learning and the world of work. This will certainly reduce the level of graduate unemployment. Hence, the missing link would have been bridged between graduates and gainful employment.

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